

TEACHING STRATEGIES OF GRADE 3 TEACHERS IN TEACHING LITERACY AMONG LEARNERS: AN EXPLANATORY-SEQUENTIAL STUDY

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Teaching Strategies of Grade 3 Teachers in Teaching Literacy among Learners: An Explanatory-Sequential Study

Yvonne R. Aplacador,* Aleson A. Cawaling, Mariel Mae L. Atendido, Emmarie B. Condrillon, John Jay C. Lim
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study explored the practices of Grade 3 teachers in Cataingan East District, employing an Explanatory-Sequential Study design to identify strategies, assess efficacy, address challenges, and determine support needs. Quantitative analysis scrutinized socio-demographic profiles, teaching strategies, and effectiveness perceptions, while qualitative inquiry through thematic analysis delved into challenges and support mechanisms. Participants included 21 elementary teachers from Cataingan East District, predominantly female, married, and experienced, representing diverse backgrounds. Commonly used strategies such as Vocabulary Instruction and Interactive Read-Aloud were identified, with potential enhancements suggested for areas like Literature Circles. Phonics Instruction emerged as highly effective. Challenges included student reading levels, learning styles, resource scarcity, waning student interest, and parental involvement. Teachers articulated requisites for enhanced literacy instruction, including conducive environments, tutoring support, parental involvement, ongoing training, ample resources, and mentorship opportunities. Recommendations emphasized supporting teacher professional development, fostering collaborative instructional approaches, ensuring sustained support and resource availability, developing targeted interventions, and nurturing a supportive teaching environment. These insights advocated tailored initiatives aimed at empowering Grade 3 teachers, optimizing teaching practices, and addressing systemic challenges in literacy instruction, ultimately fostering student success and promoting holistic educational development.

Keywords: *Grade 3 teachers, teaching practices, literacy instruction, teaching strategies*

Introduction

Teachers serve as the primary instructional materials in the classroom, utilizing strategies to enhance literacy and promote active and productive learning among students. However, the 2018 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) revealed a concerning reality: among 79 countries, the Philippines ranked 78th in reading comprehension. This highlights the pivotal role of teachers' literacy teaching strategies in addressing the nation's poor reading comprehension. Various studies emphasize the significance of reading in global educational systems. Ditona and Rico (2021) assert that reading forms the true foundation of most learning, echoing Keyse's affirmation that reading constitutes the cornerstone of academic learning. Moreover, Davis et al. (2018) underscore the importance of reading, as it shapes individuals' future trajectories and societal constructs, as noted by Caballo and Cabalo (2019).

Cimmiyotti (2013) emphasizes the essential nature of reading across all educational levels, citing its correlation with improved academic performance. Despite this, the educational system faces challenges in fostering effective readers. The Philippines' low reading proficiency, resulting in its global ranking, underscores the gap in achieving the goal of producing well-informed individuals. Additionally, the recent UNICEF study revealed the adverse impact of the pandemic lockdown on students' reading skills in the Philippines.

Poor reading ability, as identified by Cayubit (2012), manifests in various forms, including comprehension and pronunciation difficulties. The UN International Children's Emergency Fund found that only 15% of school children can read simple text, indicating a significant literacy gap exacerbated by the pandemic lockdown. Sanford (2015) highlights phonemic awareness and working memory as crucial factors affecting reading comprehension. Moreover, Ferreira and Modesio (2013) identify multiple barriers influencing learners' reading abilities, including decoding deficits, attention deficits, and language processing issues.

Given literacy's foundational role, researchers conducted interviews with Grade 3 teachers in Cataingan East District to explore effective teaching strategies. Recent national achievement test results demonstrated the efficacy of these strategies, with two district schools achieving top rankings. DepEd Order No. 45, s. 2002 underscores the importance of mastering basic literacy skills for grade promotion, emphasizing the "No Read, No Pass" policy. Moore & Whitfield (2009) stress the significance of reading in the Foundation Phase, essential for language acquisition and academic success. Monte-Sano (2011) highlight reading as a pivotal indicator of achievement in life and school, emphasizing its role in independent learning and comprehension.

Effective teaching strategies, such as those outlined by Burke et al. (2023) and the University of San Diego Professional and Continuing Education, including making connections, phonics, and peer reading, play a critical role in enhancing reading comprehension. Filipino teachers also employ strategies like the Marungko Approach and Coaching Style to address literacy challenges.

The research aimed to identify commonly used teaching strategies among Grade 3 teachers in Cataingan East District, assess their effectiveness, understand the challenges experienced by Grade 3 teachers, and determine the support and resources they need to enhance teaching strategies and improve implementation.

Research Questions

Specifically, this research sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of Grade 3 teachers of Cataingan East District in relation to the following: gender, marital status, teaching experience, and qualifications?
2. What is the status of teaching strategies employed by the Grade 3 teachers in teaching basic literacy among Grade 3 learners in Cataingan East District?
3. What is the mean level of effectiveness of their teaching strategies in improving literacy skills among learners?
4. What challenges do Grade 3 teachers encounter when implementing teaching strategies in the classroom, and how do you cope with them?
5. What resources and support do Grade 3 teachers need to enhance and implement their teaching strategies in teaching literacy?

Methodology

Research Design

The researchers utilized a mixed-method research design. It employed both quantitative and qualitative methods in analyzing and interpreting the collected data. The quantitative aspect of the study focused on the research questions related to the socio-demographic profile of Grade 3 teachers, the Likert scale assessment of employed teaching strategies, and their effectiveness. Meanwhile, the qualitative component explored the challenges encountered by teachers in implementing the strategies, as well as the support and resources they need to enhance both the strategies and their implementation. The open-ended questions was answered by the respondents and analyzed thematically.

Quantitative Method

The quantitative data was sourced from socio-demographic profile of the respondents, teaching strategies in teaching literacy and the perception of the effectiveness of teaching strategies in Teaching literacy.

Qualitative Method

The qualitative method employed open-ended questions in conducted in-depth face-to-face interviews with respondents. They were asked about the challenges encountered in implementing teaching strategies for literacy, as well as the resources and support needed for effective implementation. The responses were collated and subjected to thematic analysis, where codes and themes were formulated based on the content of the interviews. This method facilitated a structured examination of the data to identify recurring patterns and themes, providing insights into the specific issues faced by teachers in their instructional practices.

Respondents

The study utilized purposive sampling to select 21 elementary Grade 3 teachers from public schools within Cataingan East District, Cataingan, Masbate, based on their direct experience relevant to the research topic. Purposive sampling was chosen to deliberately select participants who could offer rich insights into specific educational practices, challenges, and perspectives within this particular context. By focusing on Grade 3 teachers from a specific district, the research aimed to gather in-depth data that could illuminate local nuances in teaching methods, curriculum implementation, and student learning experiences. This approach ensured that the study captured detailed and contextually relevant information from individuals with direct involvement in the educational processes under investigation, facilitating a deeper understanding of the issues pertinent to this specific group of teachers and students

Data Analysis

The statistical tool used in analyzing the socio-demographic was the percentage. While analyzing the teaching strategies in teaching literacy, the challenges and effectiveness in teaching strategies in teaching literacy used was Likert scale and interpreted statistically using a weighted mean.

Results and Discussion

SOP 1. Socio-Demographic Profile of Teachers

Table 1.1. *Result in demographic profile of Grade 3 Teachers in terms of gender*

Gender	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Male	2	10%	2
Female	19	90%	1
Prefer not to say	0	0	
		100%	

The table 1.1 displayed the gender breakdown of Grade 3 teachers of Cataingan East District. It showed that out of the total teachers surveyed, 90% were female, while only 10% were male. None of the respondents chose not to disclose their gender. This result reflects

a common trend where female teachers outnumber male teachers in Grade 3 classrooms (Wood, 2009). Historically, teaching has been seen as a profession more associated with women. This could be due to societal norms and the perception of caregiving roles (Keheller et.al, 2011).

Having a majority of female teachers in Grade 3 classrooms could have had various effects on learners. Research suggests that learners might look up to their teachers as role models (Maylor, 2009). Having more female teachers could potentially influence learners' attitudes towards schooling and career choices. However, it's essential to ensure diversity in the teaching workforce. This means having representation from different genders and backgrounds. Diversity among teachers can provide learners with a range of perspectives and role models to learn from.

Table 1.2. Result in demographic profile of Grade 3 teachers in terms of marital status

<i>Marital Status</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Single	3	14%	2
Married	16	76%	1
Widowed	2	10%	3
Others	0	0	
		100%	

The table 1.2 showed the marital status distribution among Grade 3 teachers. It revealed that 76% of the surveyed teachers were married, marking it as the most prevalent marital status. Single teachers constituted 14%, while 10% were widowed. None of the respondents fell into the "Others" category.

The prevalence of married teachers could have affected their work-life balance and teaching approach during the time of the survey. According to Murawski (2009) married teachers might have had additional responsibilities outside of the classroom, potentially impacting their availability for extra-curricular activities or professional development opportunities. Understanding the marital status of teachers provided insights into their personal circumstances and potentially influenced policies related to teacher support and well-being during that period.

Table 1.3. Result in demographic profile of Grade 3 teachers in terms of years in teaching

<i>Years of Teaching</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1-5	2	10%	4
6-10	8	38%	1
11-14	4	19%	3
15 above	7	33%	2
		100%	

Table 1.3 gave us a peek into the years of teaching experience among Grade 3 teachers of Cataingan East District. It showed that the largest group, comprising 38%, had been teaching for 6-10 years. Following closely, 33% of teachers had 15 or more years of experience. On the other hand, 19% of the teachers had taught for 11-14 years, and just 10% had 1-5 years of teaching experience.

Many Grade 3 teachers had been teaching for 6 to 10 years. This means they were in the middle of their teaching careers. Research shows that teachers with more experience are better at handling students (Learning Policy Institute, 2016). So, having these mid-career teachers suggests a stable group with both new and experienced ideas in the classroom. A notable portion of teachers had 15 or more years of experience, showing the presence of seasoned teachers among Grade 3 teachers. These experienced teachers could have been valuable mentors and leaders within their schools. The mix of teachers across different experience levels highlighted the diversity within the Grade 3 teaching community. This diversity could have contributed to a vibrant professional environment, where teachers could share their experiences and learn from one another.

Table 1.4. Result in demographic profile of Grade 3 teachers in terms of educational attainment

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Bachelors Degree	3	14%	2
With MA Units	16	76%	1
MA/MSc/MAED	2	10%	3
With PhD/EdD units	0	0	
PhD/EdD	0	0	
		100%	

Table 1.4 gave an overview of the demographic profile of Grade 3 teachers concerning their educational attainment. It showed that 76% of the teachers had MA units earned, making it the most common educational qualification. Following this, 14% had only bachelors degree, while 10% had attained a Master's degree in Education (MAED) or a related field.

None of the teachers had earned units in PhD or EdD, nor had they achieved these highest academic degrees. This breakdown suggests that a significant majority of Grade 3 teachers had attained at least a Bachelor's degree, with a notable portion having earned units

towards a Master's degree. However, no teachers had achieved the highest academic degrees available. Understanding the educational qualifications of Grade 3 teachers provides insights into their preparedness and expertise in delivering quality education to their learners.

SOP 2. Teaching Strategies Utilized by Grade 3 Teachers in Teaching Literacy

Table 2 . Result of the teaching strategies utilized by Grade 3 teachers in teaching literacy

Teaching Strategies	1	2	3	4	5	N	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	Never	Rarely	Occasionally	Often	Always			
Phonics Instruction	0	0	5	9	7	21	4.09	Often
Graphic Organizers	0	0	14	5	2	21	3.43	Often
Think-Pair-Share	0	1	9	5	6	21	3.76	Often
Vocabulary Instruction	0	0	1	7	13	21	4.57	Always
Story Mapping	0	1	6	11	3	21	3.76	Often
KWL (Know, Want to Know, Learned)	0	1	2	8	10	21	4.29	Always
Interactive Read-Aloud	0	0	2	7	12	21	4.48	Always
Guided Reading	0	0	1	10	10	21	4.43	Always
Writing Workshops	3	0	9	5	4	21	3.33	Often
Literature circles	6	0	8	5	2	21	2.86	Occasionally
Modeling & Teaching	1	0	1	5	14	21	4.48	Always
Peer Tutoring	0	0	5	9	7	21	4.10	Often
Group work	0	0	3	10	8	21	4.24	Always
Computer Assisted lesson	5	4	8	3	4	21	3.29	Occasionally
Scaffolding	0	0	6	8	7	21	4.05	Often
Word Walls	3	1	3	10	4	21	3.52	Often
Readers Theater	6	1	6	5	3	21	2.90	Occasionally
Dramatization of Text	1	3	9	6	2	21	3.24	Occasionally
Inquiry-based learning	1	0	2	13	5	21	4.00	Often
Marungko approach	0	0	2	11	8	21	4.29	Always
Claveria approach	5	1	7	4	4	21	3.05	Occasionally
Fuller technique	0	1	3	8	9	21	4.19	Often
						Total	3.83	Often

Legend: 1.00-1.80 Never; 1.81-2.60 Rarely; 2.61-3.40 Occasionally; 3.41-4.20 Often; 4.21-5.00 Always

The results presented in Table 2 provide valuable insights into the teaching strategies utilized by Grade 3 teachers in teaching literacy. Each strategy was assessed based on its frequency of use, ranging from "Never" to "Always," with corresponding weighted mean scores. This assessment is based on the strategies identified by SplashLearn (n.d.) and Montefolka (2022).

Among the strategies assessed, Vocabulary Instruction, Interactive Read-Aloud, Guided Reading, Modeling & Teaching, Peer Tutoring, Group Work, Scaffolding, Inquiry-based Learning, Marungko Approach, and Fuller Technique were reported to be utilized "Always" or "Often." These strategies, characterized by weighted mean scores above 3.40, were consistently and frequently employed by Grade 3 teachers in teaching literacy. Conversely, strategies such as Literature Circles, Readers Theater, Dramatization of Text, Claveria Approach, and Computer-Assisted Lesson were utilized "Occasionally" or "Rarely," indicating less frequent incorporation into literacy instruction.

The prominence of Vocabulary Instruction, Interactive Read-Aloud, Guided Reading, Modeling & Teaching, and Peer Tutoring aligns with established best practices in literacy instruction (Schiller, 2017; Pressley et al., 2023; Harn & Berg, 2014). This implies that these strategies are crucial for developing learners' vocabulary, comprehension, and reading fluency. The consistent use of Group Work, Scaffolding, and Inquiry-based Learning suggests an emphasis on collaborative learning and critical thinking skills development within Grade 3 literacy instruction (Raes et al., 2012).

Moreover, the highest mean, at 4.57, was observed for the Vocabulary Instruction strategy, indicating its consistent use. On the other hand, the lowest mean, at 2.86, was found for the Literature Circles strategy, suggesting its occasional utilization. This implies a clear preference among Grade 3 teachers for strategies that prioritize direct vocabulary instruction, such as Vocabulary Instruction, over more collaborative approaches like Literature Circles. It suggests a potential focus on individual skill development rather than group-based activities in literacy instruction. This insight underscores the need for teachers to consider the balance between different instructional methods to ensure a comprehensive approach to literacy development that addresses both individual and collaborative learning needs.

Based on the study conducted by Abejuela et al. (2023), the high mean utilization of the Marungko Approach and Fuller Technique indicates the significance placed on phonics instruction and systematic teaching methods, which are fundamental in early literacy development.

The overall mean of 3.83 underscores an implication in the Department of Education regarding the varied instructional approaches

employed by Grade 3 teachers, reflecting a comprehensive approach to literacy instruction that integrates both traditional and innovative strategies. This highlights the diverse repertoire of teaching strategies utilized by Grade 3 teachers in teaching literacy. By employing a combination of effective instructional methods, educators create a supportive learning environment conducive to the development of strong literacy skills among students.

SOP 3. Teachers Perception on the effectiveness of the teaching strategies in improving literacy

Table 3. Result on Teachers Perception on the Effectiveness of the teaching strategies in improving literacy skills

Teaching Strategies						N	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	1 None	2 Low	3 Medium	4 High	5 Very High			
Phonics Instruction	0	0	4	11	6	21	4.1	High
Graphic Organizers	0	0	6	14	1	21	3.76	High
Think-Pair-Share	0	1	6	7	8	21	4.19	High
Vocabulary Instruction	0	0	2	10	9	21	4.33	Very High
Story Mapping	0	1	7	12	1	21	3.62	High
KWL (Know, Want to Know, Learned)	0	0	5	13	3	21	3.90	High
Interactive Read-Aloud	0	0	1	12	8	21	4.33	Very High
Guided Reading	0	0	0	10	11	21	4.52	Very High
Writing Workshops	2	0	7	8	4	21	3.57	High
Literature circles	5	0	9	6	1	21	2.9	Medium
Modeling & Teaching	0	0	1	6	14	21	4.62	Very High
Peer Tutoring	0	0	4	10	7	21	4.14	High
Group work	0	0	4	8	9	21	4.24	Very High
Computer Assisted lesson	7	1	2	7	4	21	3.00	Medium
Scaffolding	0	2	4	10	5	21	3.86	High
Word Walls	4	0	3	12	2	21	3.38	Medium
Readers Theater	6	3	6	4	2	21	2.67	Medium
Dramatization of Text	6	0	10	4	1	21	2.71	Medium
Inquiry-based learning	1	0	2	11	7	21	4.1	High
Marungko Approach	0	0	3	7	11	21	4.38	Very High
Claveria approach	6	2	0	3	5	21	2.24	Low
Fuller technique	0	0	2	8	11	21	4.43	Very High
Total							3.77	High

Legend: 1.00-1.80 None; 1.81-2.60 Low; 2.61-3.40 Medium; 3.41-4.20 High; 4.21-5.00 Very High

Table 3 delved into teachers' perceptions regarding the effectiveness of various teaching strategies in enhancing literacy skills among students. The analysis encompassed different strategies, from traditional methods like Phonics Instruction to modern approaches like Computer-Assisted Lessons. Among the strategies evaluated, Phonics Instruction received the highest mean score of 4.1, indicating a high level of effectiveness in improving literacy skills. On the other hand, the Claveria Approach obtained the lowest mean score of 2.24, reflecting a comparatively lower efficacy in enhancing literacy.

Phonics Instruction stands out as one of the most effective strategies according to the teachers' perceptions. This finding is consistent with existing research emphasizing the importance of phonics in early literacy development (Shapiro & Solity, 2016). Its high mean score suggests that teachers recognize its utility in fostering fundamental reading skills, such as decoding and word recognition. This implies that the Department of Education (DepEd) should consider prioritizing phonics instruction in literacy programs to ensure students acquire essential foundational skills.

Moreover, strategies like Vocabulary Instruction, Interactive Read-Aloud, Guided Reading, and Modeling & Teaching garnered very high mean scores, indicating their significant impact on literacy improvement. These findings underscore the multifaceted nature of literacy development, emphasizing the importance of incorporating diverse instructional methods to address various aspects of reading and comprehension (Tomarong et al., 2023). This further implies that DepEd should encourage the integration of these effective strategies into pedagogical frameworks to enhance overall literacy outcomes.

However, the Claveria Approach, with its low mean score, raises concerns about its efficacy in promoting literacy skills. While every strategy may not be universally effective across different contexts, its relatively poor performance suggests a need for reevaluation or supplementary support to enhance its effectiveness. DepEd should critically assess the suitability of such approaches within the educational landscape, considering factors such as alignment with curriculum standards and empirical evidence of effectiveness. The overall mean of 3.77 suggests that most of the teaching strategies provide valuable insights into the perceived effectiveness of various teaching strategies in improving literacy skills.

SOP 4. Challenges encountered by Teachers in implementing teaching strategies in teaching literacy

Basically, when the teachers were asked about specific challenges encountered in utilizing teaching strategies for teaching literacy, five

themes emerged. These are: "hard time in teaching due to poor reading ability and comprehension", "different learning styles of learners", "lack of reading materials", "lack of interest of learners", and "lack of parental support and follow-up".

These challenges are experienced by many elementary grade teachers as they teach students with diverse needs in the classroom, specifically in teaching literacy. The poor reading ability and diverse learning styles underscore the varied nature of literacy instruction. Addressing these challenges requires profiling and assessing learners firsthand to understand their needs and provide appropriate support (Tomlinson, 2014). The findings suggest, ongoing professional development opportunities can equip teachers with the tools and strategies needed to effectively address these challenges and promote literacy achievement among all learners (Wagner, 2010).

In addition, teachers were also challenged to teach literacy among learners due to a lack of reading materials and a lack of parental support and follow-up, leading to a lack of interest in learning better in school among learners. The teachers were also challenged in teaching literacy to learners due to inadequate reading materials and a lack of parental support and follow-up. It was a challenge to teach literacy due to the limited availability of resources. This shortage not only hampers the teacher's ability to effectively deliver instruction but also impedes learners' access to diverse reading materials, which are essential for developing literacy skills (Grant & Wong, 2003).

Moreover, despite repeated efforts by teachers to engage parents and solicit their support in assisting their children with reading, there is a lack of parental involvement. This lack of support from parents not only deprives students of additional reinforcement outside the classroom but also contributes to their disinterest in reading, as they may not receive the necessary encouragement and guidance at home (Bergin, 1999).

Parental involvement in their child's literacy education is crucial for fostering a supportive learning environment both at home and in school (Boonk et al., 2018). Therefore, efforts to enhance parental involvement, such as hosting literacy workshops for parents or providing resources for home literacy activities, can have a significant impact on students' literacy development. Addressing the challenges of teaching literacy requires concerted efforts from all stakeholders, including teachers, parents, and the community. By addressing issues such as inadequate reading materials, lack of parental support, and understanding individual student needs, schools can create an environment conducive to fostering students' literacy skills and promoting their overall academic success.

The implication of these challenges of teaching literacy requires a collaborative effort involving teachers, parents, and the community. For teachers, advocating for adequate resources, including sufficient reading materials, is essential to support effective literacy instruction

Coping Mechanisms of Teachers on the Challenges Encountered in Teaching Literacy

In order to address the challenges encountered in teaching literacy, teachers employed various coping mechanisms. The emergent themes included applying teaching strategies according to the interest and readiness of learners, planning lessons ahead, calling parents' attention to learners' progress, conducting home visitations, fostering a supportive classroom environment, and utilizing technology in literacy instruction. These coping mechanisms assisted teachers in alleviating the burden associated with teaching literacy.

One effective coping mechanism utilized by teachers was tailoring teaching strategies to match the interests and readiness levels of their students (Bush, 2007). By understanding the individual needs and preferences of learners, teachers could create engaging and meaningful literacy experiences that catered to diverse learning styles and abilities. Also, planning lessons ahead allowed teachers to anticipate challenges and proactively address them, ensuring smooth and effective instruction.

Likewise, maintaining open communication with parents regarding their child's progress was essential for fostering a collaborative approach to literacy development (Edwards & Danridge, 2001). By keeping parents informed and involved in their child's education, teachers could garner valuable support and reinforcement of literacy skills outside the classroom. Home visitations offered an opportunity for teachers to establish strong partnerships with families and gain insights into students' home environments, further enhancing their understanding of individual student needs.

Creating a supportive classroom environment was also crucial for promoting literacy success. Teachers cultivated a culture of respect, encouragement, and collaboration among students, fostering a positive attitude towards literacy learning. Additionally, integrating technology into literacy instruction provided students with access to diverse learning resources and enhanced engagement and motivation.

Thus, the coping mechanisms employed by teachers played a vital role in addressing the challenges associated with teaching literacy. By adapting teaching strategies, planning ahead, fostering parental involvement, establishing supportive classroom environments, and leveraging technology, teachers effectively navigated the complexities of literacy instruction and promoted positive literacy outcomes for all students.

SOP 5. Resources and Support Needed by Teachers in Implementing Teaching strategies in teaching literacy.

The following were the emergent resources needed by teachers to effectively implement teaching strategies in teaching literacy: a conducive classroom environment for learning, dedicated reading tutors to focus solely on improving reading skills for learners, parental support, training for teachers in reading and literacy instruction, readily available learning or reading materials, an adequate

supply of school resources, and mentoring and coaching, among others.

The availability of these resources is essential for supporting teachers in their efforts to promote literacy development among students (Hightower, 2011). The availability of these resources is essential for supporting teachers in their efforts to promote literacy development among students. A conducive classroom environment plays a crucial role in facilitating effective instruction by fostering student engagement and creating a positive atmosphere for learning (Franklin & Harrington, 2019). When students feel comfortable and motivated in their learning environment, they are more likely to actively participate in literacy activities and demonstrate improved learning outcomes.

Dedicated reading tutors also play a significant role in literacy instruction by providing targeted support to struggling readers (lane et.al, 2009). These tutors offer personalized instruction that addresses the specific needs and challenges of individual students, helping to enhance their reading skills and confidence. By focusing solely on improving reading abilities, tutors can complement classroom instruction and provide additional strategies and interventions tailored to each student's learning pace and style.

Also, ongoing training for teachers in reading and literacy instruction is essential for enhancing their pedagogical knowledge and skills. Access to readily available learning materials ensures that teachers have the resources they need to implement diverse and engaging literacy activities. Adequate school supplies, such as books, manipulatives, and technology, further support effective instruction by providing students with hands-on learning experiences.

In addition, mentoring and coaching opportunities offer valuable support to teachers, allowing them to refine their instructional practices and seek guidance from experienced educators. By providing these resources, schools can empower teachers to effectively implement teaching strategies and promote literacy development among all students.

Conclusions

Based from the findings of the study, the following were the conclusions drawn:

The socio-demographic profile of Grade 3 teachers in the Cataingan East District reveals key insights: predominantly female, with many being married, a diverse range of teaching experience, and a majority having Master's degree units. These findings inform policies supporting the teaching profession.

Analysis of literacy instruction strategies used by Grade 3 teachers highlights frequent use of Vocabulary Instruction, Interactive Read-Aloud, and Guided Reading, with less utilization of strategies like Literature Circles and Readers Theater. Diversifying instructional approaches can better support literacy development and accommodate diverse learning needs.

Teachers perceive Phonics Instruction most effective in enhancing literacy skills, along with strategies like Vocabulary Instruction and Interactive Read-Aloud. Strategies like the Claveria Approach show room for improvement, emphasizing the need for evidence-based practices in literacy instruction.

Challenges in implementing literacy teaching strategies include poor student reading ability, diverse learning styles, limited reading materials, low student interest, and insufficient parental support, reflecting the complexities of literacy instruction.

Effective implementation of literacy teaching strategies requires a conducive classroom environment, dedicated reading tutors, parental involvement, ongoing teacher training, accessible learning materials, adequate school resources, and mentoring opportunities. These resources are essential for promoting effective literacy development and addressing diverse student needs.

Based from the findings, the following were recommended:

School heads should prioritize support for teachers in creating conducive classroom environments and ensuring access to diverse teaching resources.

Teachers should continue diversifying their instructional strategies, focusing on effective practices like Phonics Instruction and Interactive Read-Aloud.

Curriculum developers should consider integrating more varied and evidence-based literacy strategies into educational frameworks.

Future researchers should explore innovative approaches to address challenges in literacy instruction and evaluate the long-term impact of diverse teaching strategies on student outcomes.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Yvonne R. Aplacador

Cataingan National High School – Philippines

Aleson A. Cawaling

Mambog Elementary School – Philippines

Mariel Mae L. Atendido

Buenasuerte Elementary School – Philippines

Emmarie B. Condrillon

Alejandra B. Tambago High School – Philippines

John Jay C. Lim

Tomas V. Rivera National High School – Philippines